

Baltic MUPPETS

DELIVERABLE 5.1

INNOVATION CALL DOCUMENTS KIT

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Grant agreement number	101083785
Project title	Baltic MUPPETS Baltic Mussel Products for pet foods
Deliverable title	Innovation Call documents Kit
Deliverable number	5.1
Deliverable version	1
Contractual date of delivery	30/11/2024
Actual date of delivery	30/11/2024
Document status	Final
Online access	Yes
Diffusion	PU - Public
Nature of deliverable	R- Document, Report
Work Package	5
Contributing partners	N/A
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Keywords	Innovation Call

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document serves as a comprehensive collection of all essential documents governing the Baltic MUPPETS Innovation Call. The Innovation Call is designed to engage innovative SMEs and start-ups across the Baltic Sea region in the technological advancements of the mussel value chain. By formalizing third-party financing rules, these documents provide clear guidance and structure to applicants throughout the application, evaluation, and funding process.

The following key documents are included:

- Guidelines for Applicants, information regarding the Baltic MUPPETS project and the scope and objectives of the Innovation Call;
- Proposal template, following the online application form, available at F6S platform (<https://www.f6s.com/baltic-muppets-innovation-call>);
- Sub-grant Agreement template, providing a template of the sub-grant agreement that the successful applicants providing will be requested to sign;
- Declaration of Honour template, providing that all conditions of the Innovation Call are accepted by an SME legal representative;
- SME Declaration template, which evaluates the status of the SMEs participating in Innovation call;
- Bank account information template, collecting information about the applicant's bank account where the Baltic MUPPETS payments will be sent to.

These documents establish a transparent framework that supports SMEs and start-ups in proposing, executing, and managing funded projects that align with Baltic MUPPETS' goals for environmental sustainability and economic growth in the Baltic Sea region.

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Baltic MUPPETS

BALTIC MUPPETS INNOVATION CALL - GUIDELINES FOR APPLICANTS

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1. Baltic Muppets project overview

1.1. The concept

Due to low salinity, the Baltic Sea blue mussels are often smaller and have therefore not been preferred for human consumption. In commercial blue mussel farms where the salinity is higher, small mussels are considered a side-stream of market size mussel production. Nevertheless, mussel meat contains the same amino acid composition as fish meal and can be used as a sustainable raw material in pet food.

1.2. The project

The goal of Baltic MUPPETS is to develop, scale and commercialise complete value chains for small blue mussel-based pet-food products. The main goal of the project is to valorise this unused resource through the cooperation of three demonstrator sites in Sweden, Denmark and Germany. The project works on three different business cases, all using innovative submerged farming techniques (to avoid ice, reduce costs and increase public acceptance), and ultimately creating high value pet food products. Baltic MUPPETS will also co-develop business cases for additional products from small mussel side-streams and conduct market research to evaluate the profitability of the three demonstrators' business cases. The financial and environmental value of the ecosystem services provided by the farms will be assessed, with efforts made to create tangible, concurrent benefits in terms of sustainable development (both scientific and economic), blue growth (economic) and job creation (societal).

The Baltic MUPPETS project - Baltic MUssel Products for PET-foodS - is implemented under the Grant Agreement no. 101083785, within the framework of the ERDF Interregional Innovation Investments Instrument (I3) of the European Commission.

2. Innovation call overview

2.1. The innovation call

The Baltic MUPPETS Innovation Call invites innovative start-ups and SMEs from selected regions to propose solutions that drive sustainable business strategies and technological advancements within the mussel value chain. This initiative aims to accelerate the market uptake of mussel-based products and services, promoting environmental sustainability, fostering economic growth, and supporting ecosystem restoration efforts.

This call will fund projects in two key areas: testing and piloting activities, particularly for submerged mussel farms, and feasibility studies, market analysis, and business strategy development, complementing ongoing investments in Baltic MUPPETS mussel farms and market research. The call is open to eligible regions in Sweden, Germany, Denmark, Estonia, and Ireland, and offers a 5-month project period.

This document outlines the general terms, objectives, and eligibility criteria for applicants. All associated Annexes must be read carefully before the submission of an application.

The open call will fund projects that address the two following clusters:

- **Testing and piloting activities:** Solutions for submerged mussel farms, including testing and piloting of harvesting systems, regulatory requirements, and logistic solutions.
- **Feasibility study, market study, and business strategy development:** Feasibility and market studies, strategies to overcome market barriers, increase consumer acceptance, assess pricing, recommend certifications, and explore new revenue streams from mussel farming products and services with focus on high-value pet food.

2.2. Innovation Call Budget

The total available funding for the Innovation Call is **€100.000,00**. Selected SMEs will receive up to **€50.000,00 each** to implement projects addressed to the selected challenges within the eligible regions.

Table 1: Innovation Call budget details

Maximum funding per SME	up to 50.000,00 €
Type of financial support	Lump sum
Innovation Call total budget	100.000,00€

2.3. Innovation Call Timeline

Table 2: Innovation Call budget details

Baltic MUPPETS Innovation Call timeline	
Call opening date	5 November 2024
Call closing date	14 January 2025, 17:00 CET (Brussels time)
Eligibility check	January 2025
Internal evaluation	February 2025
Announcement of results	February 2025
Sub-grant agreement signature	February 2025
Selected projects implementation	1 March 2025 – 31 October 2025 <i>(total program of 5 months that offers flexibility in start date)</i>

3. Innovation Call Challenges

The following section outlines the specific challenges and opportunities available for applicants in two key areas:

Cluster 1 - Testing and Piloting Activities

Cluster 2 - Feasibility Studies, Market Strategies, and Business Plans.

These clusters focus on developing innovative solutions for mussel farming and mussel-based products, ultimately creating high value pet food products, with a strong emphasis on testing, market readiness, and scaling up promising ideas.

Applicants are invited to submit project proposals aimed at addressing the challenges described in each cluster. The selected proposals will not only contribute to the sustainable growth of the mussel farming industry but also address critical environmental concerns, such as eutrophication, remediation, nutrient extraction, and improved water quality, while opening new commercial opportunities for small mussels.

Technical solutions to be funded under Cluster 1 are expected to be at the level of maturity of TRL 6. Actions to be funded under Cluster 2 must be related to the main investments of Baltic Muppets which start at TRL6.

For each challenge SMART goals have been identified. SMART goals are **S**pecific, **M**easurable, **A**chievable, **R**elevant, and **T**ime-bound.

Cluster 1 - Testing and piloting activities

Challenge #1.1 Test solutions for submerged farms - Assessment of durability and stability of ropes (Sweden)

In Sweden, four different types of ropes are used as substrate for the growth of mussels at specific mussel farming sites in the open sea and these ropes perform differently, in terms of harvest biomass per meter rope. The performance of a certain rope-type is different between different farm locations, for example, one type of rope performs well at one farm-site but is useless on another site, presumably because of different environmental conditions. It is difficult to tell in general which type of rope is best, because there is no “one type fits all” solution.

The criteria for good performance are:

1. The mussels should not fall off the rope during growth, or when pulled up from the water at harvest.
2. The ropes should not get twisted around themselves while hanging in the water.
3. Substrate from the ropes should not get ripped off by the harvester and end up in the harvest.

The selected applicant should evaluate the performance of different ropes at different sites, coupled with site-specific conditions (e.g. exposure, current, strength of byssus thread attachment by the mussels). The expected result is the development of expertise on which ropes to use in low-saline waters and in different site conditions.

The selected challenge will require for the applicant to travel to the Ecopelag mussel farms in Västervik, Norrstensfjärden and St. Anna, where the different rope-types are in use. Additionally, it might be required to follow the harvest team to design a sampling method for evaluation of rope wear and tear.

Table 3: SMART TARGET for Challenge 1.1.

Specific	The report from the study will analyse the optimal type of substrate for spat collection and mussel production at the mussel farms in Västervik, Norrstensfjärden, and St. Anna.
Measurable	The study will analyse four types of substrates at three locations from May to October 2025. Mussel density, size distribution, and biofouling will be reported.
Achievable	The three mussel farms are established, and the study will be supported by boat time.
Relevant	To optimize spat collection and mussel production, site-specific knowledge of substrate types is essential.
Time	May - October 2025 <i>(total program of 5 months that offers flexibility in start date due to potential changes in environmental conditions).</i>

Challenge #1.2 Test solutions for submerged farms - Regulatory requirements, such as marking systems to document ownership. (Denmark)

According to the Danish regulation, all elements on a Mussel farm must be marked with a unique code to identify the equipment owner. The marking system should be robust, and it should allow

the read of the unique number after the equipment has been submerged and exposed to biofouling. This includes the development of a marking system with the possibility of identifying unique codes to be applied to the equipment.

Testing activities should focus on stability and readability of ownership marks. The performance of the marks may be evaluated according to:

- Easy to attach to the farm elements.
- The mark must be robust according to seawater and the processing.
- The tacks should be readable for >20 y.
- Easy to read by the mussel farmer and the authorities.
- Reading should not be affected by biofouling.
- The cost of the system should be below 1 EUR per mark.

The system must be tested at a submerged mussel farm in the Limfjord (Denmark) on different types of equipment (pipes, nets, concrete blocks, markings etc.). The selected applicant shall do the marking of the equipment and monitor the performance of the marks. Taking into consideration the budget limitation, another possibility would be to develop a marking system, a plan for tests and a manual for the implementation of outcomes of tests.

Table 4: SMART TARGET for Challenge 1.2.

Specific	The report and three prototypes from the study will analyse the most efficient methods for marking mussel farming equipment, focusing on the stability and readability of the ownership marks. Three types of marks will be tested on a submerged mussel farm in the Limfjord.
Measurable	The marks will be evaluated based on the following criteria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ease of attachment to farm elements. • Robustness against seawater and processing conditions. • Durability: Marks should remain readable for over 20 years. • Ease of reading by mussel farmers and authorities. • Resistance to biofouling: Readability should not be compromised by biofouling. • Cost-effectiveness: The system should cost less than 1 EUR per mark.
Achievable	Danish law requires that all equipment be marked. While various types of marks exist in the market, they have not yet been tested on mussel farms.
Relevant	Danish mussel farmers must mark all equipment, so developing or identifying the best mark will streamline the marking process and improve efficiency.
Time	March - October 2025 <i>(total program of 5 months that offers flexibility in start date due to potential changes environmental conditions).</i>

Challenge #1.3 Pilot the solution for submerged farms - New logistic solutions for harvested mussels. (Sweden)

The project proposal must focus on innovative, resource efficient and sustainable piloting activities of the selected solution to evaluate the performance of the selected solution in a real-world, operational environment before full-scale implementation. The proposal should focus on piloting solutions.

In the low saline part of the Baltic Sea, it takes 2 years for a blue mussel to reach good size for harvest. Harvest is performed with a specialized floating harvest machine, and because of the high costs associated with the harvest, it is important to optimize the transport of harvested mussels from the offshore farm to quay.

When mussels are harvested, they are still alive and will continue to live as long as they are kept in good conditions. However, at harvest they are collected in dense packed bags and stored in the open air. Under those conditions, the time that the mussels can survive limits the time available for collection and transport to quay, and the time available for further transport and processing.

The harvester has a limit of ca 5 tons per day and the smallest reasonable amount to transport to the quay is 15 tons. The selected applicant should evaluate feasibility of harvesting limits, taking into consideration conditions for survival of mussels. The identified problem is the survival of the mussels, which depends on water temperature and density of packaging. In addition to clarifying time-limits for harvest and transport with today's methods, the applicant should also research which harvest and storage conditions could possibly be improved, in order to increase the time of survival.

The access to relevant premises may be granted for the 3rd party to pilot selected solutions (special conditions may apply). Pilots can also be conducted on a site with similar conditions.

Table 5: SMART TARGET for Challenge 1.3.

Specific	The report from the study will analyse how to optimise logistics in mussel production on the east coast of Sweden. The logistics include harvesting, transport, and storage of the mussels before processing. The report will propose two technical solutions for an integrated process and estimate the investment cost.
Measurable	The analysis will propose two different integrated technical solutions for harvesting, transport, and processing. Investment and operational costs will be estimated for both solutions.
Achievable	The existing European processing industry for mussels uses technology that must be adapted to small, thin-shelled mussels from the Baltic.
Relevant	Optimized logistics will reduce cost and improve the quality of the product.
Time	May - October 2025 <i>(total program of 5 months that offers flexibility in start date due to potential changes environmental conditions).</i>

Cluster 2 - Feasibility study, market study, business strategy

Challenge #2.1 Strategy on how to overcome barriers for market entry of new mussel products

The project proposal must examine the obstacles to the market introduction of new mussel products - pet food products based on small mussels.

The project proposal must propose a strategy to overcome the barriers and offer solutions to reach the market and target group. The strategy should include a market overview of already existing pet food products made from mussels in Germany, Sweden and Denmark and an analysis of the different characteristics such as prices, packaging sizes, main product characteristics (e.g. canned wet food, mussels only as an additive, dry food, frozen food, barf, etc.).

New products may also include the sale of goods and services derived from shellfish farming, such as nutrient extraction, improvement of water quality and biodiversity, and the use of shellfish to build biogenic reefs.

Table 6: SMART TARGET for Challenge 2.1.

Specific	<p>This challenge aims at identifying potential obstacles for sale and consumption of mussel-based pet food products, as well as ideas how to overcome these. Potential obstacles can be found in (unpleasant) smell, price, why a product is bought by customers, shelf life, packaging, form of application, and the novelty of the product itself, which might require additional explanation.</p> <p>Mussel food and its particular properties should be compared to already existing food products, and specific advantages/benefits of mussel products (e.g. health benefits, attractive price, regionality, traceability of sources) and particularly the environmental benefits should be identified.</p>
Measurable	Measurable results will be a report on the customers experience with mussel pet food resulting in a ranking of the obstacles that according to the impact on potential customer decision.
Achievable	A survey on the a.m. topics of 5(+) retailers and 50(+) end consumers is achievable
Relevant	Crucial for market success of product
Time	March – July 2025

Challenge #2.2 Strategy to increase consumer acceptance for mussel products

The project proposal shall study consumer acceptance for mussel products, especially petfood products, by performing a research analysis of consumer acceptance for mussel products. The proposal should bring detailed characteristics of consumers and their needs regarding mussel-based pet products and provide a tailored strategy for increasing consumer acceptance in Sweden/Germany/Denmark. The strategy should cover analysis of what kind of products pet

owners look for and what special characteristics (e.g. GAGs for joint health, product “X” makes shiny fur etc.) of mussel-based pet products would be desirable.

Table 7: SMART TARGET for Challenge 2.2

Specific	Challenge 2.2 aims at understanding and increasing the consumer acceptance of mussel pet-food products. This challenge is linked to challenge 2.1 and a cooperation between both should be established. The already performed consumer survey by CRM should be used as a base to be extended to Sweden and Denmark. The study should result in a list of preferences for purchase decision.
Measurable	A market analysis and potential increase of turnover of mussel products must be prepared, including the analysed and evaluated surveys in Denmark and Sweden.
Achievable	An online survey in Denmark and Sweden, and an elaborated campaign
Relevant	Crucial for market success of product
Time	March – July 2025

Challenge #2.3 Go-to-market strategy with assessment of willingness to pay for mussel products

The project proposal shall study the mussel products market landscape, customer preferences and positioning of mussel products. The proposal should also survey potential customers to gather data on customer preferences regarding the price of mussels’ products. The strategy should cover analysis of pricing models, market surveys and gathering consumer feedback.

Table 8: SMART TARGET for Challenge 2.3

Specific	An overview about already existing mussel products on the pet food market, including prices must be prepared. Also, a research on the role of price for the purchase decision in the world of pet food general and – more specifically – for mussel-based products is expected.
Measurable	A study on willingness to pay for mussel-based pet food products in relation to turnover, considering the various advantages of mussels.
Achievable	A survey of 100(+) people is conducted either online or in person.
Relevant	Important to give an orientation for feasibility and pricing of mussel pet-food products.
Time	May –October 2025

Challenge #2.4 Recommendation for certification to improve mussel production

The project proposal shall propose a study of the certification to improve mussel production. This includes a list of standards and benefits for the identified certificates and provide criteria and compliance requirements for each certificate. Additionally, the study should provide relevant information concerning requirements to obtain the certification. The proposed study shall evaluate not only international certification systems, but also focus on regional alternatives. Moreover, it should conduct a gap analysis to determine the current state of mussel production processes in relation to the standards of the desired certifications. It needs to include the identification of areas which need improvement to meet the certification desirable requirements relevant to at least mussel farm in the following countries: Germany/Denmark/Sweden.

Table 9: SMART TARGET for Challenge 2.4

Specific	The aim of this challenge is to research the role and importance of organic labels (producer labels, EU-label, regional labels), identify specific differences and requirements for producers. On the basis of a concrete example of a not yet certified farm, work and financial effort in order to gain a specific certification should be demonstrated.
Measurable	Report about the role and importance of organic certification for end-consumers. A list of eco-labels in Germany, Denmark, and Sweden. A concrete scenario for a farm including effort, costs and potential turnover effect.
Achievable	A report on the should be delivered.
Relevant	Orientation of mussel farms about potential economic benefits by eco-labelling for mussel farmers.
Time	March –July 2025

Challenge #2.5 Sales of goods and services from mussel farming

The project proposal shall include a study for market goods and services from mussel farming, including sale of nutrient catch, sales of improved water quality, sales of improved quality of bathing water, sales and relaying of mussels for habitat restoration of biogenic reefs. The study should identify relevant market partners, important selling points, need of process guarantees and pricing of the product relevant to at least one mussel farm in these countries: Germany/Denmark/Sweden.

Table 10: SMART TARGET for Challenge 2.5

Specific	A report will analyse goods and services from mussel farming, the market for selling these assets—including private and public buyers—market mechanisms, and sales points for different segments. The report will address the impact of new EU regulations such as the Habitat Restoration Law and the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD).
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Measurable	The report will be structured as a matrix, detailing 1) type of ecosystem service, 2) potential market for the service, 3) price, and 4) sales arguments. It will also forecast the impact of the Habitat Restoration Law and the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD).
Achievable	There is extensive scientific knowledge on goods and services from mussel farming, and the market for habitat restoration and investment in sustainable projects, particularly for improving CSRD reporting, is expanding.
Relevant	The sale of goods and services related to habitat restoration presents a potential secondary value chain for mussel farms, which needs to be developed.
Time	March – July 2025

4. Eligibility Criteria

This section describes in detail who can apply and what conditions should be met by the submitted proposal.

4.1. Who can apply?

The Baltic Muppets Innovation Call is open to **single applicants as an SMEs/start-up (Micro, small and medium-sized enterprises)**.

Micro, small and medium-sized enterprise (SMEs) will be considered eligible **ONLY** if complying with the [Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC](#) and [the SME user guide](#).

In summary, the criteria which define an SME are:

- a) The headcount in the Annual Work Unit (AWU) is less than 250.
- b) Annual turnover less or equal to €50 million OR annual balance sheet total less or equal to €43 million.

Start-ups that do not have yet an annual turnover or balance sheets are also considered eligible given that they fulfil the criteria (a) and (b) at submission time.

Applicants will be considered eligible if they comply will **the following rules**:

- a. Applicant fulfils the conditions for SME or start-up, described in the section 4.1.
- b. Applicant has not been declared bankrupt or has initiated bankruptcy procedure.
- c. Applicant has not been convicted for fraudulent behaviours, other financial irregularities, unethical or illegal business practices.
- d. Applicant is not under liquidation or an enterprise under difficulty according to the Commission Regulation No 651/2014 art. 2.18.

- e. Applicant has not been excluded from the possibility of obtaining EU funding under the provisions of both national and EU law, or by a decision of both national or EU authority.

4.2. Eligible regions

Applicants should be legally registered in the regions covered by the Baltic Muppets Consortium, including partners & associated partners regions (Fig. 1; Table 3):

Table 11: regions covered by the Baltic Muppets Consortium

Country	Regions	NUTS II code
Sweden	Stockholm	SE11
	Småland och öar	SE21
	Södra Sverige	SE22
Germany	Berlin	DE30
	Schleswig-Holstein	DEF0
Denmark	Sjælland	DK02
	Midtjylland	DK04
	Nordjylland	DK05
Estonia	Eesti	EE00
Ireland	Northern and western	IE04

Figure 1: Regions covered by the Baltic Muppets Consortium

4.3. Proposal eligibility

- a) Each applicant can submit only **one** proposal. At the application stage, the criteria of time will be applied, as only the last submitted proposal to the F6S platform is going to be taken into consideration for further analysis.
- b) Each applicant can only address **one challenge** mentioned in Section 3.
- c) Applications for the Baltic Muppets Innovation Call must be submitted in English. Submissions in any other languages will be considered ineligible and will not be evaluated.
- d) The total budget per proposal project may not exceed **€50.000,00**. Also, the total amount requested must represent 100% of the total project costs.
- e) Proposals will not be accepted from entities who are partners (beneficiaries) or affiliated entities/ linked-third parties to the Baltic MUPPETS consortium, or who are formally linked in any way to them.

5. How to apply?

This section explains the submission process and defines the rules and procedures on how to apply to the Innovation Call.

5.1. How to submit your proposal

The applicants can submit their proposals exclusively through the F6S platform:

<https://www.f6s.com/baltic-muppets-innovation-call/apply>

The submission window opens on the **5th of November 2024 and closes on 14th of January 2025, at 17:00 CET.**

Applications submitted via any other channels will be automatically rejected. The applicants are required to **create a profile at www.f6s.com** to be able to submit their proposal.

The proposal template - **Baltic MUPPETS Proposal template** is available on the Baltic MUPPETS website: <https://balticmuppets.eu/opportunities/innovation-call/>. The template is extracted as a document for reference purposes only. The Application form should be directly filled out at the F6S platform.

We recommend becoming familiar with the templates of: **Baltic MUPPETS Sub-grant agreement, SME declaration and Declaration of Honour**. These documents must be provided if the applicant is selected and are mandatory to finalise the contract and enter the project implementation phase.

We strongly recommend not waiting until the last moment for proposal submission. **Failure of the proposal to arrive in time for any reason, including communications delays, or network issues is not acceptable as an extenuating circumstance and will automatically lead to rejection of the submission.** The time of receipt of the proposal as recorded by the submission system will be definitive.

Important: Please note that after application submission, editing is not possible. If an error is discovered and the call deadline has not passed, the applicant may request a resubmission by contacting the Baltic Muppets Innovation Call team at support@f6s.com, using the subject line: "RESUBMISSION REQUEST". While we will make every effort to process resubmission requests, we cannot guarantee the feasibility of resubmitting before the deadline if the request is not received in a timely manner.

All decisions made by the Baltic Muppets Innovation Call team regarding submission and resubmission are final.

6. How will applications be evaluated and selected?

This section defines the rules and procedures which will be performed for the evaluation of the Innovation Call and selection of innovators.

Figure 2: Evaluation of the Innovation Call

6.1. Evaluation steps

The evaluations will take place remotely and will be organised in the following steps:

- **Step 1: Eligibility Check:** An initial eligibility check will be carried out to verify that the applications meet the conditions expressed in section 4 and to discard non-eligible applications.
- **Step 2: Individual Internal Evaluation:** Each application will be assigned to at least two experts, involved in the Baltic Muppets consortium. The experts will perform an individual evaluation.
- **Step 3: Consensus:** After the individual evaluation, the internal experts will have a consensus meeting to agree on a common evaluation text and a score.
- **Step 4: Ranking lists:** At the end of the evaluation, a ranking will be prepared with the shortlisted applications.

6.2. Step 1: Eligibility Check

An initial eligibility check will be performed to filter and discard non-eligible proposals. All proposals must meet the following criteria:

1. Submission has been made only in English through the F6S platform and by the defined deadline [Y/N].
2. The applicant submitted only one proposal, which is fully completed, including all required sections [Y/N].
3. The applicant is an SME/startup legally registered and established in one of the eligible regions covered by the Call.
4. The total budget of the proposal does not exceed €50,000, representing 100% of the project costs.
5. Applicants and proposal met all conditions described in Section 4 [Y/N]

Proposals must meet **ALL the eligibility criteria**. Proposals that do not meet one or more of the criteria will be deemed non-eligible and discarded. Eligible proposals will be shortlisted for the next step of the evaluation process.

Applicants whose proposals are deemed non-eligible will be notified via email after the eligibility check has been concluded.

6.3. Steps 2 - 4: Selection

6.3.1. Selection criteria

The applications will be scored based on the criteria shown in the table 4 below.

Table 12: Selection Criteria

Criteria	Description
Criterion 1: Concept and approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Alignment with the Baltic Muppets project and the challenge selected. ● Coherence and plausibility of the application. ● Innovation, novelty and feasibility of the proposed solution and approach.
Criterion 2: Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Quality and feasibility of the work plan and the concept fit to a 5-month programme. ● Quality and feasibility of the described scenario of the testing or piloting activities (challenge dedicated to piloting or testing activities) or plan for preparing the strategy (challenges dedicated to strategies).
Criterion 3: Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The expected impact of the proposed solution. ● Exploitation potential of the proposed solution beyond the project timeline.
Criterion 4: Team and value for money	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Demonstrated capacity to implement the proposed solution. ● Knowledge, technological and business expertise. ● Allocation and justification of resources and project costs.

Each criterion under examination exhibited in Table 4 will receive score values that are represented by the rationale detailed in the table 5 below.

Table 13: score values

Score	Rationale
1 - Poor	The application addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.
2 - Fair	The application addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.
3 - Good	The application addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary.
4 - Very Good	The application addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.
5 - Excellent	The application successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.

Each criterion will be scored between 1 and 5. Half point scores are not given. The final score (including for each criterion) is calculated based on the average of the scores provided by the evaluators. The threshold for each criterion is three (3), therefore any criterion with a score less than three will disqualify the application.

At the end of the evaluation process, all applications will be ranked into two ranking lists, one per each Cluster. Threshold: only proposals scoring at least 3 points (out of 5) in each criterion will be considered for funding.

The ranking will follow the rules:

- **Rule 1:** The applications will be ranked based on their final score.
- **Rule 2:** If there is a tie between applications, these will be ranked according to the following order:
 - Best score on *Concept and Approach* (Criterion 1);
 - Best score on *Implementation* (Criterion 2);
 - Best score on *Impact* (Criterion 3);
- **Rule 3:** In case following Rule 2 there are proposals in the same position, priority will be given to the application that has a lower funding request.

6.3.2. Final selection of proposals

Priority to fund and invite to sign the contract will be given to applications addressing **Cluster 1 - Testing and Piloting Activities taking into account the budget of Innovation Call and total requested budget by applicants.**

In case no proposals are submitted to Cluster 1, or proposals from Cluster 1 score below 3 points, or the Innovation Call budget will not be entirely used, proposals from Cluster 2 will be selected.

6.3.3. Notification of the results

All applicants will be notified of the results of the evaluation and will receive an Evaluation Summary Report (ESR).

6.4. Reserve list

Baltic Muppets will keep a reasonable number of applications in a reserved list, in case any applicant decides to withdraw or is not able to fulfil the contract requirements.

6.5. Redress process

Within 3 working days of the delivery of a rejection letter considering the application as non-eligible or an ESR, the applicant may submit a request for redress if they believe the results of the eligibility check have not been correctly applied, or if they feel that there has been a shortcoming in the way their application has been evaluated that may affect the final decision on whether to enter the Baltic Muppets Programme for Innovators.

In such a case, an internal review committee from Baltic Muppets will examine the applicant's request for a redress. The committee's role is to ensure a coherent interpretation of such requests, and equal treatment of applicants. Requests for redress must:

- Be related to the evaluation process or eligibility checks.
- Clearly describe the complaint (in English).
- Sent by the entity's legal representative that has also submitted the proposal.

The committee will review the complaint and will recommend an appropriate course of action. If there is clear evidence of a shortcoming that could affect the eventual funding decision, it is possible that all or part of the application will be re-evaluated. Please note:

- This procedure is concerned only with the general evaluation and/or eligibility checking process. The committee will not question the scientific or technical judgement of the evaluators.
- A re-evaluation will only be carried out if there is evidence of a shortcoming that affects the final decision on whether to fund the proposal or not. This means, for example, that a problem related to one evaluation criterion will not lead to a re-evaluation if a proposal has failed anyway on other criteria.
- The evaluation score following any re-evaluation will be regarded as definitive. It may be lower than the original score.

All requests for redress will be treated in confidence and must be sent to the Baltic Muppets team at: opencall@BalticMuppets.eu.

7. What is next? Sub-grant agreement signature

After the final project selection, the contract preparation phase will start in collaboration with the representatives of the projects that have been awarded. We will ask the selected proposals to

provide the necessary documents which are mentioned in the table 6 below. All documentation requires a signature and must be signed with a valid electronic digital signature.

Table 14: necessary documents to sign the sub-grant agreement

Requirement	Description
Proof of legal existence	Company Register, Official Gazette or another official document per country showing the name of the organisation, the legal address and registration number and a copy of a document proving VAT registration (in case the VAT number does not show on the registration extract or its equivalent).
<p>Specific to SMEs</p> <p>1. Proof of the SME condition is required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the applicant has been fully validated as an SME on the Beneficiary Register Participant Portal, the PIC number must be provided. • If the applicant has not been fully validated as an SME on the Participant Portal, the following documents will be required to prove the status as an SME: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ SME Declaration signed (with a valid e-signature) and stamped: In the event the beneficiary declares being non-autonomous, the balance sheet and profit and loss account (with annexes) for the last period for upstream and downstream organisations is required. ○ Status Information Form, which includes the headcount (AWU), balance, profit & loss accounts of the latest closed financial year and the relation, upstream and downstream, of any linked or partner company. <p>2. Supporting documents:</p> <p>In cases where either the number of employees or the ownership is not clearly identified: any other supporting documents which demonstrate headcount and ownership such as payroll details, annual reports, national regional, association records, etc.</p>	
Know Your Customer (KYC) form	The document to collect the proof of Identity and proof of address from Directors of selected applicants to see if they are a Politically Exposed Person (PEP) or have been sanctioned.
Sub-grant agreement	The contract signed between the Baltic MUPPETS Consortium represented Treasurer (F6S) and the beneficiary. Contract as provided to the sub-grantee is final and may not be changed.
Declaration of Honour	The Document which covers all conditions related to the Baltic MUPPETS Innovation Call signed by the legal representative of the applying entity.
Bank Account information	The account where the funds will be transferred will be indicated via a specific form signed by the entity.

It should be emphasised that each participating SME should provide at contract preparation time a valid VAT number¹. Failure to provide a valid VAT number will automatically result in exclusion from the contract preparation.

Please make sure you provide documents within the deadlines that will be communicated to you. If you fail to deliver the requested documents on time, without clear and reasonable justification, you will be excluded from the further formal assessment and you will be replaced by the applicant from the Reserve List. In general, the negotiation should be concluded **within 2 weeks**.

8. Funding Programme - selected entities obligations

8.1. Implementation and reporting

Selected applicants participating in the Baltic MUPPETS Innovation Call will be responsible for the following duties:

8.1.1 Project Implementation:

The projects will run up to 5 months. Applicants must adhere to this timeline and demonstrate tangible progress throughout the implementation phase.

8.1.2 Project stages and Reporting:

Projects will be divided for up to 3 stages and will follow requirements as shown in the stage schedule described below in table 7.

At the end of each stage, applicants will have to deliver the assigned report or deliverable as a means of verification of work performed. Each report and deliverable will be evaluated as means to check the progress of the project implementation.

Table 15: stages of selected project

Stage name	Outcome of the stage	Timeline
Stage 1	Deliverable - detailed implementation plan	within 15 days after the start of the project
Stage 2	Mid-term report	By the last day of the stage implementation
Stage 3	Final report /deliverable	within 10 days after completing the project

8.1.3 Project Contact Point:

¹ To be checked at European Commission services such as http://ec.europa.eu/taxation_customs/vies/

Each selected project will be assigned a dedicated person (Project Contact Point) from the Baltic MUPPETS consortium. The Project Contact Point will provide guidance, monitor progress, and ensure that the project aligns with the predefined goals. The Project Contact Point will be the key point of contact for the applicants and will assist in overcoming any challenges faced during the project implementation.

8.2 Financial support provided

Successful proposals shall receive the requested financial contribution in the form of a lump sum, following the payment schedule. The detailed payment schedule and payment conditions will be stated in the Sub-grant (Beneficiary) Agreement.

Eligible costs

A lump sum funding is a grant based on a pre-fixed lump sum amount and not based on the reimbursement of actual costs. The lump sum must approximate the beneficiaries' underlining actual costs. The following direct costs, incurred during the project's duration, are eligible:

- 1. Direct staff costs (personnel):** hours cost of the staff of the beneficiary that is dedicated to actual work under the development of the project;
- 2. Equipment costs:** depreciation costs of equipment and only eligible for projects funded under Cluster 1 - Testing and piloting activities.
- 3. Other direct costs:** further direct incurred costs can be claimed, like travel expenses, consumables, etc. Travel expenses will be eligible only for projects funded under Cluster 1 - Testing and piloting activities.
- 4. Indirect costs:** 7% calculated as (personnel costs + equipment costs + other direct costs) *0.07.
- 5. Subcontracting is not allowed.**

The granting of a lump sum does not foresee the delivery of a detailed financial report on actual costs and timesheets.

8.3. Payment scheme

Successful proposals shall receive the requested financial contribution in the form of a lump sum, following the payment schedule described below.

Table 16: payment schedule

Payment number	Amount	Timeline
1st payment	30% of the total funding paid	within 14 days after the positive review of deliverable - detailed implementation plan
2nd payment	40% of the total funding paid	within 14 days after the positive review of mid-term review
3rd payment	30% of the total funding paid	within 30 days after final report approved by the consortium

9. Additional considerations

9.1. Conflict of interest

Applicants must not have any current and/or potential conflict of interest with the Baltic Muppets Innovation Call selection process and during the whole programme. Applicants must formally and immediately notify the Baltic Muppets project of any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interest and take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

All cases of conflict of interest will be assessed case by case. Applicants must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective evaluation and implementation of the project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests').

If a conflict of interest is discovered and confirmed at the time of the evaluation process, the application will be considered as non-eligible and will not be evaluated.

9.2. Checks and reviews

The EC may, at any time during the implementation of the sub-project and up to five years after the end of the sub-project, arrange for a check and review to be carried out by external auditors, or by the EC services themselves, including the European Anti-Fraud office (OLAF). The procedure shall be deemed to be initiated on the date of receipt of the relevant letter sent by the EC.

9.3. Promoting the action and giving visibility to the EU funding

The third parties which will receive funding must promote the sub-project, the Baltic Muppets project and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner and to highlight the financial support of the EC. Further details will be provided in the Sub-Grant Agreement, and the Baltic Muppets Communication team will guide and support these communication activities.

9.4. Intellectual Property Rights

The results and IPR developed during the sub-granted project implementation will be the exclusive property of the corresponding beneficiary.

The third parties must comply with IP rules outlined in the Baltic MUPPETS Sub-Grant Agreement (template). In general terms, this includes the following aspects:

- The granting consortium - Baltic Muppets - will not obtain ownership of the results generated under sub-granted projects. However, the Baltic Muppets Consortium will be granted the right to make internal use of any results produced by the third party as part of their Baltic Muppets Innovation Call activities.
- The results generated under sub-granted projects will remain the property of the third party.
- The third party will be responsible for any costs associated with protection of Intellectual Property Rights.

9.5. Data protection

To process and evaluate applications, the Baltic Muppets consortium will need to collect Personal and Industrial Data. F6S Network Ireland Limited, as the Innovation Call Manager of the project, will act as Data Controller for personal data submitted through the F6S platform for these purposes. Please see the privacy policy [here](#). F6S Network Ireland Limited, as the Baltic Muppets FSTP Treasurer, will also have access to this information.

A Data Protection Officer (DPO) has been appointed by F6S to ensure compliance with data protection regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and that personal data is collected, processed, and stored in a secure manner.

The F6S platform's system design and operational procedures ensure that data is managed in compliance with The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). Each applicant will accept the F6S terms to ensure coverage. Please refer [here](#) to review the F6S platform's privacy policy and data security policy.

Apart from the F6S platform, data will also be stored in the F6S Google Drive, and in the project repository on SharePoint, managed by the SUBMARINER Network - the Baltic Muppets Project Coordinator.

The Baltic Muppets consortium must retain generated data until five years after the balance of the Baltic Muppets project is paid or longer if there are ongoing procedures (such as audits, investigations, or litigations). In this case, the data must be kept until the end.

10. Important links and contacts

The Baltic Muppets consortium will provide information to the applicants primarily via <https://www.f6s.com/baltic-muppets-innovation-call/discuss> so that all information (questions and answers) will be accessible to all potential applicants. No binding information will be provided via any other means.

- More info about Baltic Muppets: <https://balticmuppets.eu/>
- More info about the Baltic Muppets Innovation Call: <https://balticmuppets.eu/opportunities/innovation-call/>
- Apply via: <https://www.f6s.com/baltic-muppets-innovation-call/apply>
- Online Q&A and discussion forum: <https://www.f6s.com/baltic-muppets-innovation-call/discuss>
- Help desk: opencall@balticmuppets.eu
- F6S support team (for platform issues during the application): support@f6s.com

Baltic MUPPETS

BALTIC MUPPETS INNOVATION CALL - APPLICATION FORM TEMPLATE

APPLICANT INFORMATION

1. Organisation name
2. VAT number
3. PIC number
4. Country and Region where the organisation is legally registered
Please Indicate in which region your organization is based, from the options below (Baltic MUPPETS regions):

- Sweden - Stockholm
- Sweden - Småland and Islands
- Sweden - South Sweden
- Germany - Berlin
- Germany - Schleswig-Holstein
- Denmark - Zealand
- Denmark - Mid-Jutland
- Denmark - North Jutland
- Ireland - Northern and western
- Estonia – Eesti

5. Website
6. Main contact person
7. Contact person's role/position in the company
8. E-mail address

PROPOSAL IDENTIFICATION

9. Title of the proposal
Please provide the title of the project which can be used publicly if the project gets selected
10. Acronym of the proposal
11. Summary of the proposal

Please provide a summary of your project that can be published if the project is selected for funding. Outline main objective of proposal, expected results and impact.

12. Challenge of the proposal.
Please select the challenge you aim to address with your proposal. To be eligible, the proposal must address only ONE challenge.

- Challenge #1.1. Test the solution for submerged farms - assessment of durability and stability of ropes
- Challenge #1.2. Test the solution for submerged farms - regulatory requirements such as marking systems to document ownership.

- Challenge #1.3. Pilot the solution for submerged farms - new logistic solutions for harvested mussels.
- Challenge #2.1 Strategy on how to overcome barriers to go to the market with new mussels' products
- Challenge #2.2. Strategy to increase consumer acceptance for mussels' products
- Challenge #2.3. Go to the market strategy with assessment of willingness to pay for mussels' products
- Challenge #2.4. Recommendation for certification to improve production of mussels
- Challenge #2.5. Sale of good and services from mussel farming

PROPOSAL INFORMATION

CONCEPT AND APPROACH

13. Please describe main idea of your proposal and expected outcomes within the timeline of the project implementation. (4000 characters)
14. Please explain how your proposal will address the challenge, and the problem described in challenge. (4000 characters)

Description of challenges can be found in the document: Innovation Call - Guidelines for Applicants available at: <https://balticmuppets.eu/opportunities/innovation-call/>

IMPLEMENTATION

15. Selected project can last up to 5 months. Please describe how project will be implemented. Describe the scenario of the testing or piloting activities (Cluster 1 challenges) or plan for delivering the strategy (Cluster 2 challenges) and how you will reach the envisioned scenario. (6000 characters)
16. Selected project will be divided for up to 3 stages, at the end of each stage, applicants will have to deliver the assigned report or deliverable as a mean of verification of work performed. Please describe work plan and timeline with a breakdown of the work into tasks/subtasks and deliverables or milestones. (6000 characters)

IMPACT

17. Please describe the expected impact and benefits of your proposal. (4000 characters)
18. Please describe potential dissemination and exploitation of the results and what activities you will undertake to ensure the exploitation is successful. (4000 characters)

APPLICANT AND TEAM:

19. Please describe the competences of the organization including company profile and main products/services (if relevant) and business and technical expertise. (4000 characters)
20. Please provide description of team involved in project implementation, their role and expertise/experience useful for the project implementation. (4000 characters)

BUDGET

21. Maximum amount of funding for single SME is €50.000 in a form of a lump sum. Please indicate total requested budget in EUR.
22. Please provide a breakdown of project costs and brief justification (4000 characters)
*Direct staff costs (personnel): hours cost of the staff of the beneficiary that is dedicated to actual work under the development of the project; Equipment costs: depreciation costs of equipment and only eligible for projects funded under Cluster 1 - Testing and piloting activities. Other direct costs: further direct incurred costs can be claimed, like travel expenses, consumables, etc. Travel expenses will be eligible only for projects funded under Cluster 1 - Testing and piloting activities. Indirect costs: 7% calculated as (personnel costs + equipment costs + other direct costs) *0.07. Subcontracting is not allowed.*

ETHICS AND SECURITY:

23. Ethics:

	YES / NO
Informed consent	
Informed consent	
Does the proposal involve children?	
Does the proposal involve patients or persons not able to give consent?	
Does the proposal involve adult healthy volunteers?	
Does the proposal involve Human Genetic Material?	
Does the proposal involve Human biological samples?	
Does the proposal involve Human data collection?	
Research on human embryo/foetus	
Does the proposal involve Human Embryos?	
Does the proposal involve Human Foetal Tissue / Cells?	
Does the proposal involve Human Embryonic Stem Cells?	
Privacy	
Does the proposal involve processing of genetic information or personal data (e.g., health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction)	

Does the proposal involve tracking the location or observation of people?	
Research on animals	
Does the proposal involve research on animals?	
Are those animals transgenic small laboratory animals?	
Are those animals transgenic farm animals?	
Are those animals cloned farm animals?	
Are those animals nonhuman primates?	
Research involving developing countries	
Use of local resources (genetic, animal, plant etc)	
Benefit to local community (capacity building i.e., access to healthcare, education etc)	
Dual use	
Research having direct military application	
Research having the potential for terrorist abuse	
ICT implants	
Does the proposal involve clinical trials of ICT implants?	
I CONFIRM THAT NONE OF THE ABOVE ISSUES APPLY TO MY PROPOSAL	

24. Security

Please indicate if your project will involve:

- Activities or results raising security issues: [YES/NO]
- 'EU-classified information' as background or results: [YES/NO]
- Any potential "dual use" of results: [YES/NO]

25. Ethics Self-Assessment

If you have entered any ethics issues in the Ethics/ Security checklist, you must upload ethics self-assessment as a PDF document which:

- Provides a rationale for the option made.
- Describes how the proposal meets the national legal and ethical requirements of the country or countries where the tasks raising ethical issues are to be carried out.
- Explains in detail how you intend to address the issues in the ethical issues table, as regards: a) Research objectives (e.g., study of vulnerable populations, dual use, etc.) b) Research methodology (e.g., clinical trials, involvement of children and related consent procedures, protection of any data collected, etc.) c) The potential impact of the research (e.g., dual use issues, environmental damage, stigmatisation of particular social groups, political or financial retaliation, benefit-sharing, malevolent use, etc.).

Please also include the documents that you need under national law (if you already have them), e.g.: a) An ethics committee opinion; The document notifying activities raising ethical issues or authorising such

activities. If these documents are not in English, you must also submit an English summary of them (containing, if available, the conclusions of the committee or authority concerned). If you plan to request these documents specifically for the project you are proposing, your request must contain an explicit reference to the project title.

REQUIREMENTS TO JOIN BALTIC MUPPETS FUNDING PROGRAMME

26. Declaration of Honour: I confirm that I accept all conditions in Baltic MUPPETS Innovation Call - Declaration of Honour SME and information contained therein and that it will be provided signed and stamped should this proposal be accepted for funding.

Yes/No

27. SME Declaration: I confirm that the company I represent is a valid SME, following established EU rules, which validity will be proved by a signed and stamped declaration to be provided should this proposal be accepted for funding.

Yes/No

28. I accept that the information provided and submitted in this proposal can be shared by F6S with the Baltic MUPPETS consortium for the purpose of managing the programme

Yes/No

REFERRALS AND ACCEPTANCE OF TERMS AND CONDITIONS

29. Acceptance of the Baltic MUPPETS Innovation Call conditions: I have reviewed and accept all conditions of the Baltic MUPPETS Innovation Call Guidelines for Applicants.

The terms and conditions of the programme are defined in the Baltic MUPPETS Innovation Call guidelines for applicants available at: <https://balticmuppets.eu/opportunities/innovation-call/innovation-call-offer/>

Yes/No

30. How did you hear about Baltic MUPPETS Innovation Call?

31. Are you interested in being contacted about future funding opportunities?

Baltic MUPPETS

**BALTIC MUPPETS
INNOVATION CALL
-
SUB-GRANT AGREEMENT
TEMPLATE**

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Contracting parties

This **Agreement** ('the Agreement') is **between** the following parties:

On the one part,

F6S Network Ireland Limited (F6S), established in 77 Lower Camden Street, Dublin D02 XE80, Ireland, VAT number IE3629141FH, represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by Mr. Nuno Varandas, legal representative of F6S, **acting on behalf of Baltic MUPPETS consortium and as Treasurer of the Baltic MUPPETS consortium;**

Hereinafter referred to as the "Treasurer",

And, on the other part,

[Redacted] **[Organisation name/ Individual name]**
established in **[Redacted]**, **[Official address]**, VAT
number **[Redacted]**, represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by
[Redacted] **[Name of legal representative]**,

Hereinafter referred to as the "Beneficiary".

Hereinafter, all parties above are collectively referred to as the "Contracting Parties"

The Contracting Parties **HAVE AGREED** to the following terms and conditions including those in the following Annexes, which form an integral part of this Sub-Grant Agreement (hereinafter referred as the "Contract").

General Provisions

The European Commission (hereinafter referred as the "EC") and the Treasurer, as partner and representative of the **Baltic MUPPETS consortium**, have signed the Grant Agreement no. **101083785** for the implementation of the Baltic MUPPETS project – Baltic MUssel Products for PET-foods – within the framework of the ERDF Interregional Innovation Investments Instrument (I3) of the European Commission.

The Baltic MUPPETS project is implemented by the Coordinator - **SUBMARINER Network For Blue Growth EEIG**: established in in KARTENERSTRASSE 20, BERLIN 10827, Germany, **acting as Coordinator of the Baltic MUPPETS consortium and as coordinator of the Baltic MUPPETS project**, in collaboration with the other Baltic MUPPETS partners. The Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners have among themselves entered into a written agreement detailing their respective rights and obligations towards each other for carrying out the Baltic MUPPETS project and exploiting the results thereof ("the Consortium Agreement" or "CA").

The objective of Baltic MUPPETS is to develop new value chains for small mussels (1-3 cm) from the Baltic Sea for pet food and to develop innovative technologies for farming, harvesting, and processing mussels. The project will enable a new circular economy in the Baltic Sea Region as well as provide support to mussel farmers across Europe to develop, diversify, and scale their existing businesses.

The Beneficiary has been selected for funding under the **Baltic MUPPETS – Innovation Call** based on the positive evaluation of evaluators.

This Contract aims at defining the framework of rights and obligations of the Contracting Parties with respect to the Beneficiary's participation in the **Baltic MUPPETS – Innovation Call**.

The funding to be received by the Beneficiary is property of the EC. The Coordinator and the Treasurer are mere holders and managers of the funds.

Article 1 - Entry into force and termination of the contract

1.1. Entry into force

This Contract will enter into force on the day of its signature by the last Contracting Party. The Treasurer will sign this contract only after all the following documents have been received from the Beneficiary:

- The signed Declaration of Honour;
- SMEs Declaration form;
- Bank Account Information form.

All documents, properly signed, shall be sent to the Treasurer, to the following e-mail: **opencalls@balticmuppets.eu**.

The contact details of the Beneficiary for notices and communication under this contract are:

Name of contact person	
Address	
E-mail	
Telephone/ mobile phone	

1.2. Contract termination

This Contract will automatically terminate at the end of Baltic MUPPETS Funding Programme, which will happen when the Beneficiary has fulfilled all obligations in Article 2, except for those obligations that according to their content are intended to remain in effect, which keep their full force and effect (e.g., reporting on exploitation activities).

The Coordinator shall be entitled to terminate this Contract by written notice with immediate effect if the Beneficiary does not fulfil its obligations (see Article 3 - Breach of Contractual obligations).

Irrespective of the automatic termination of this Contract under present Article 1.2 or any early termination under Article 4, all obligations that according to their content are intended to be in effect for longer shall remain in effect.

Article 2 - Obligations and responsibilities of the Beneficiary

The obligations and responsibilities are defined in detail in Annex 1 - Guidelines for Applicants.

Additionally, the Beneficiary shall take every necessary precaution to avoid any risk of conflict of interest relating to economic interests, political or national affinities, personal or any other interests liable to influence the impartial and objective performance of the sub-project. In case the Beneficiary is involved in a conflict of interest or in a risk of a conflict of interest, the Beneficiary must formally notify this situation to the Coordinator without delay and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

Furthermore, the Beneficiary shall provide true and accurate documentation and declarations as defined in Article 1.1.

Article 3 - Breach of contractual obligations

In the event of a breach of the contractual obligation's representations or warranties by the Beneficiary under this Contract, the Coordinator, in coordination with the Baltic MUPPETS Consortium, reserves the right to terminate the Contract by written notice with immediate effect, even if such non-fulfilment is due to Force Majeure.

In the event of the breach of the contractual obligations by the Beneficiary, the Treasurer with the agreement of the Coordinator reserves the right of not fulfilling the respective payment to the Beneficiary.

The Coordinator also reserves the right to claim a refund of any already paid funds, both in case of breach of contract and/or in case the work/costs are not approved by the EC.

The Coordinator will give written notice requiring that such breach to be remedied within 30 days.

In case the Beneficiary has not brought remedies from the notice, the Coordinator may decide to terminate the contract unilaterally.

Article 4 – Financial contribution and financial provisions

4.1. Maximum financial contribution

The maximum financial contribution to be granted to the Beneficiary shall not exceed the amount of **xxxxxxxxxxxxx euros (xxx.xxx,00) EURO**.

4.2 Distribution of the financial contribution

The financial contribution to be granted to the Beneficiary will be calculated and distributed in accordance with the provisions set in Annex 1 - Guidelines for Applicants.

The financial grant to be paid will always be subject to:

- Provision of a report and a favourable review by the Baltic MUPPETS internal evaluation team responsible for assessing the sub-project in each of the stages.
 - Stage 1 – 30 % of the budget.
 - Stage 2 – 40 % of the budget.
 - Stage 3 – 30 % of the budget.

Note: A non-favourable review of the work carried out at the end of any stage may lead to the early termination of the contract and suspension of payments.

- The prior notice to the Beneficiary of the date and amount to be transferred to its bank account (Annex 5 - Bank account information form), providing the relevant references.
- Payments to the Beneficiary will be made by the Treasurer. In particular:
 - The Treasurer, with the agreement of the Coordinator, reserves the right to withhold the payments in case the Beneficiary does not fulfil its obligations and tasks as per Annex 2 - Proposal.
 - Banking and transaction costs related to the handling of any financial resources made available to the Beneficiary will be covered by the Beneficiary.
 - Payments will be released no later than thirty (30) calendar days after the notification to the Beneficiary that the work and deliverable associated to a particular stage has been approved.

The Beneficiary is responsible for complying with any tax and legal obligations that might be attached to this Contract.

4.3 Payments schedule

The payment schedule is directly linked to the relevant stages of the sub-project as identified in Article 4.2. The payment in each stage will be disbursed once all work related to a specific stage has received positive assessment, supported by the report or deliverable submitted to the Baltic MUPPETS team.

[Table with the payments schedule]

The financial contribution will be made to the Beneficiary by the Treasurer. During the contractual procedure, the Beneficiary will be asked to provide the respective bank account information to which the payments will be made.

The Beneficiary should submit to Baltic MUPPETS the report or deliverable corresponding to each stage no later than ten (10) calendar days after the end of the respective stage, providing sufficient time for the Baltic MUPPETS consortium to review it. A review will be held between fifteen (15) to thirty (30) calendar days after the end of the stage so that the Contracting Parties can present their work and provide answers to questions from the Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners.

The payments will be made to the Beneficiary subject to the receipt of an invoice or a filled out Financial Identification Form (FIF).¹ If the Beneficiary chooses to send an invoice, the invoice must include the following information:

- Project **xxx** – Grant no. **xxx**
- **Baltic MUPPETS – Innovation Call**
- The Stage to which the payment is associated [**Stage 1, Stage 2, Stage x**]
- Beneficiary information (e.g. sub-project acronym and beneficiary name)

The invoice or the FIF is to be sent to e-mail: **opencalls@balticmuppets.eu**. Payments will only be initiated once the work has been approved. Payments will be made no later than thirty (30) calendar days after receipt of the invoice or FIF to the bank account of the Beneficiary. All payments will be made in Euros.

NOTE: If at any of the payment stages the Baltic MUPPETS team considers that the quality of work demonstrated and/or reported does not correspond to what has been agreed, the two parties may agree to a resubmission of a deliverable and respective reassessment. If significant improvements are not delivered after the reassessment and the sub-project is therefore considered to be in breach of their contractual obligations, Baltic MUPPETS reserves the right to terminate the contract as outlined in Article 3 – Breach of contractual obligations.

Article 5 - Liability

5.1 Liability of the Beneficiary

The Beneficiary shall fully and exclusively bear the risks in connection with the fulfilment of its tasks and obligations under this Contract. Except in case of force majeure (Article 8), the Beneficiary must compensate the Coordinator, the Treasurer and the EC for any damage they sustain because of the implementation of the obligations of the Beneficiary under this Contract or because the tasks and obligations of the Beneficiary were not implemented in full compliance with this Contract.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/about_the_european_commission/eu_budget/fich_sign_ba_gb_en_0.pdf

Accordingly, neither Baltic MUPPETS Consortium nor the EC can be held liable for any damage caused to the Beneficiary or to third parties because of implementing this Contract, including for gross negligence. At the same time, neither Baltic MUPPETS consortium nor the EC can be held liable for any damage caused by the Beneficiary or third parties, because of implementing this Contract.

The Beneficiary shall bear sole responsibility for ensuring that its acts within the framework of this Contract do not infringe third parties' rights. There is no joint liability between the Contracting Parties. For this purpose, the Beneficiary shall indemnify and hold the Coordinator, the Treasurer and the EC harmless from and against all repayments, loss, liability, costs, charges, claims or damages which the Coordinator, the Treasurer or the EC as a result thereof would incur or suffer or must pay to the EC or any third parties. In addition, should the EC have a right of recovery against Baltic MUPPETS consortium regarding any or all the financial support granted under this Contract, the Beneficiary shall repay the sums in question in the terms and on the date specified by the Coordinator.

5.2 Exclusions of liability

To the extent acceptable under applicable law, in no event shall the Coordinator or other Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners be liable to the Beneficiary for loss or damage caused by the Coordinator or the Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners, their employees, agents and subcontractors in connection with this Contract for any of the following, however caused or arising, on any theory of liability, and even if the Coordinator and/or any other Baltic MUPPETS consortium partner were informed or aware of the possibility thereof:

- Loss of profits, revenue, income, interest, savings, shelf-space, production, and business.
- Opportunities; lost contracts, goodwill, and anticipated savings.
- Loss of or damage to reputation or to data.
- Costs of recall of products.
- Any type of indirect, incidental, punitive, special, or consequential loss or damage.

In respect of any information or materials from the Baltic MUPPETS consortium made available to the Beneficiary under this Contract, no warranty or representation of any kind is made, given, or implied as to the sufficiency, error-free performance, or fitness for purpose, nor as to the absence of any infringement of any proprietary rights of third parties. Therefore, in particular, but without limiting the foregoing:

- The Beneficiary shall in all cases be entirely and solely liable for the use to which it puts such information and materials, and the consequences of such use, and
- Neither the Coordinator, the EC nor the other Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners shall be liable vis-à-vis the Beneficiary in case of infringement of proprietary rights of a third party resulting from the Beneficiary's use of the information and material.

The exclusions and limitations stated in this Article and any other clause of this Contract that has as its object or effect the exclusion or limitation of liability, shall not apply in respect of any: fraud; death, injury to natural persons or damage to real or immovable property caused by the negligence or wilful act, wilful misconduct, wilful breach; or otherwise in so far as mandatory applicable law overrides such exclusions and limitations.

Article 6 - Confidentiality

6.1 Principles

Regarding all information of whatever nature or form as is disclosed between the Contracting Parties in connection with the Sub-project and identified in writing as confidential, the terms of this Article shall apply.

6.2 Obligations

All information, in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Contracting Party (the “Disclosing Party”) to the other Contracting Party (the “Recipient”) in connection with the implementation of the **Baltic MUPPETS – Innovation Call** and which has been explicitly marked as “confidential” at the time of disclosure, or, when disclosed orally, has been identified as confidential at the time of disclosure and has been confirmed and designated in writing within 15 calendar days from oral disclosure (at the latest) as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is “Confidential Information”.

The Recipient hereby accepts, in addition and without prejudice to any commitment on nondisclosure towards the EC, for a period of 5 (five) years after the end of the Contract:

- Not to use Confidential Information other than for the purpose for which it was disclosed.
- Not to disclose Confidential Information without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party.
- To ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis.
- To return to the Disclosing Party, or destroy, on demand, all Confidential Information that has been disclosed to the Recipient, including all copies and to delete all information stored in a machine-readable form to the extent practically possible. The Recipient may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive, or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable laws and regulations or for the proof of on-going obligations provided that the Recipient complies with the confidentiality obligations herein contained with respect to such copy for as long as the copy is retained.

The Recipient shall be responsible for the fulfilment of the above obligations on the part of their employees or third parties involved in the implementation of **Baltic MUPPETS – Innovation Call** and shall ensure that they remain so obliged, as far as legally possible, during and after the end hereof and/or after the termination of the contractual relationship with the employee or third party. The Recipient shall apply the same degree of care regarding the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the project as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care. Each Contracting Party shall promptly advise the other Contracting Party in writing of any unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation, or misuse of Confidential Information after it becomes aware of such unauthorised disclosure, misappropriation, or misuse.

6.3 Exceptions to the obligation of confidentiality

The information above (Article 6.2) shall not apply for disclosure or use of Confidential Information, if and in so far as the Recipient can show that:

- The Confidential Information has become or becomes publicly available by means other than a breach of the Recipient’s confidentiality obligations.
- The Disclosing Party subsequently informs the Recipient that the Confidential Information is no longer confidential.

- The Confidential Information is communicated to the Recipient without any obligation of confidentiality by a third party who is to the best knowledge of the Recipient in lawful possession thereof and under no obligation of confidentiality to the Disclosing Party.
- The disclosure or communication of the Confidential Information is foreseen by provisions of the Grant Agreement.
- The Confidential Information, at any time, was developed by the Recipient completely independently of any such disclosure by the Disclosing Party.
- The Confidential Information was already known to the Recipient prior to disclosure.
- Disclosure of the Confidential Information follows mandatory applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order.

6.4 Authorised disclosure(s)

If any Party becomes aware that it will be required, or is likely to be required, to disclose Confidential Information to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order, it will, to the extent it is lawfully able to do so under the laws and legislation applicable to said Party, prior to any such disclosure:

- Notify the Disclosing Party, and
- Comply with the Disclosing Party's reasonable instructions to protect the confidentiality of the information.

The Baltic MUPPETS Coordinator's disclosure of Confidential Information to the EC and/or the other Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners shall be governed exclusively by the terms of the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement.

Accordingly, nothing in this Contract shall prevent the Baltic MUPPETS Coordinator from complying with its obligations, including its reporting obligations, towards the EC and the other Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners, and any such disclosures shall be subject to the terms of the Grant Agreement or Consortium Agreement.

Likewise, the Beneficiary agrees and acknowledges that the EC shall be entitled to disclose Confidential Information to its staff, other EU institutions and bodies or third parties, if:

- This is necessary to implement the Grant Agreement or safeguard the EU's financial interests.
- The recipients of the information are bound by an obligation of confidentiality.

Article 7 - Intellectual property rights

The Beneficiary acknowledges that all tools, modules and similar of the Baltic MUPPETS partners are proprietary and owned by the respective Baltic MUPPETS partner or applicable third party.

Nothing in this Contract shall transfer to the Beneficiary or other partners it represents any license or other rights for the use of the tools, modules and similar that are property of an Baltic MUPPETS partner, unless a specific agreement is established.

The results developed during the sub-project shall be exclusively the property of the Beneficiary. This does not exclude the possibility for specific agreements to be made between the Beneficiary and one or more of the partners of Baltic MUPPETS.

Article 8 - Force Majeure

“Force Majeure” means any unforeseeable exceptional situation or event beyond the Contracting Parties control, which prevents either of them from fulfilling any of their obligations under the Agreement, which was not attributable to error or negligence on their part and which proves to be inevitable despite the exercising of all due diligence.

Any default of a service, defect in equipment or material or delays in making them available, unless they stem directly from a relevant case of force majeure, as well as labour disputes, strikes or financial difficulties cannot be invoked as Force Majeure.

The Contracting Parties shall take the necessary measures to limit any damage due to Force Majeure. They shall do their best to resume the implementation of the action as soon as possible.

No Contracting Party shall be in breach of its obligations and tasks if such a breach is caused by Force Majeure. A Contracting Party will notify the other Contracting Party of any Force Majeure as soon as possible. In case the Beneficiary is not able to overcome the consequences of Force Majeure within thirty calendar (30) days after such notification, the Baltic MUPPETS Coordinator will decide accordingly, including the termination of the Contract.

Article 9 - Information and communication

9.1 Information and communication towards the EC

The Beneficiary shall, throughout the duration of the sub-project, take appropriate measures to engage with the public and the media about the sub-project and **to highlight the financial support of the EC and the Baltic MUPPETS project.**

Unless the EC requests otherwise, any publicity, including at a conference or seminar or any type of information or promotional material (brochure, leaflet, poster, presentation etc.), and any infrastructure, equipment, and major results must:

- Specify that the sub-project has received funding from the EC through the Baltic MUPPETS project.
- Display the European emblem along with the Baltic MUPPETS logo. When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence. This obligation to use the European emblem in respect of projects to which the EC contributes implies no right of exclusive use. It is subject to general third-party use restrictions which do not permit the appropriation of the emblem, or of any similar trademark or logo, whether by registration or by any other means. Under these conditions, the Beneficiary is exempt from the obligation to obtain prior permission from the EC to use the emblem.
- Specify that it reflects only the author’s views and that the EC and the Baltic MUPPETS Consortium is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The following text should be used:

“The [sub-project acronym] has indirectly received funding from ERDF Interregional Innovation Investments Instrument (I3) of the European Commission, via the Baltic MUPPETS – Innovation Call issued and executed under the Baltic MUPPETS project (Grant Agreement no. 101083785).”

The Coordinator, the Baltic MUPPETS consortium, and/or the EC shall be authorised to publish, in whatever form and on or by whatever medium, the following information:

- The name of the Beneficiary.
- Contact address of the Beneficiary.
- The general purpose of the sub-project (publishable summary, etc.)

- The amount of the financial contribution of the EC foreseen for the sub-project. after the final payment, the amount and rate of the financial contribution of the EC accepted by the EC.
- The estimated amount and rate of the financial contribution of the EC foreseen for the Beneficiary in the table of the estimated breakdown of budget.
- The geographic location of the activities carried out.
- The list of dissemination activities and/or of patent (applications) relating to foreground.
- The publishable reports submitted (technical reports are excluded, since they are confidential).
- Any picture or any audio-visual or web material provided to the EC in the framework of the Sub-project.

The Beneficiary shall ensure that all necessary authorisations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the Baltic MUPPETS Coordinator, the Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners, or EC does not infringe any rights of third parties.

Upon a duly supported request by the Coordinator on behalf of the Beneficiary, the EC may agree to forego such publicity if disclosure of the information indicated above would risk compromising the beneficiary's security, academic or commercial interests.

9.2 Information and communication among the Contracting Parties

Any notice to be given under this Contract shall be in writing to the addresses and recipients listed above. Any change of persons or contact details shall be notified immediately to the Baltic MUPPETS Coordinator. The address list shall be made accessible to all parties concerned.

Article 10 - Checks and reviews

The EC may, at any time during the implementation of the sub-project and up to five years after the end of the sub-project, arrange for a check and review to be carried out, by external auditors, or by the EC services themselves, including the European Anti-Fraud office (OLAF). The procedure shall be deemed to be initiated on the date of receipt of the relevant letter sent by the EC.

There will be no financial checks, reviews, or audits to check costs, since beneficiaries have no obligation to document the costs incurred for the action. Checks, reviews, and audits will focus on the technical implementation of the action.

The Beneficiary shall make available directly to the EC all information and data that may be requested by the EC or any representative authorised by it, in view of verifying that the Grant Agreement is properly managed and performed in accordance with its provisions.

The Beneficiary shall keep the originals or, in exceptional cases, duly authenticated copies (including electronic copies) of all documents related to the Grant Agreement for up to five years from the end of the sub-project. These shall be made available to the EC when requested during any check under the Grant Agreement.

To carry out these checks, the Beneficiary shall ensure that the EC's services and any external body(ies) authorised by it have on-the-spot access at all reasonable times, notably to the Beneficiary's offices, to its computer data, and to all the information needed to carry out those checks. They shall ensure that the information is readily available on the spot during an audit and, if so requested, that data be handed over in an appropriate form.

Based on the findings made during the check, a provisional report shall be drawn up. It shall be sent by the EC or its authorised representative to the Beneficiary concerned, which may make observations thereon within one month of receiving it. The EC may decide not to take into account observations

conveyed or documents sent after that deadline. The final report shall be sent to the Beneficiary concerned within two months of expiry of the aforesaid deadline.

Based on the conclusions of the check, the EC shall take all appropriate measures which it considers necessary, including the issuing of recovery orders regarding all or part of the payments made by it and the application of any applicable sanction.

The European Court of Auditors shall have the same rights as the EC, notably right of access, for the purpose of checks and audits, without prejudice to its own rules.

In addition, the EC may carry out on-the-spot checks and inspections in accordance with Council Regulation (Euratom, EC) No 2185/96 of 11 November 1996 concerning on-the-spot checks and inspections carried out by the EC to protect the European Communities' financial interests against fraud and other irregularities.

Article 11 – Data protection

The Contracting Parties have the obligation to abide by the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons regarding the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

Each Contracting Party shall each be considered a separate and independent data controller, as defined in the GDPR, to every other Contracting Party. The processing of personal data shall be carried out lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner, collected for specific purposes and adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which it is processed. Where it might be designated by a relevant Supervisory Authority or through agreement between Contracting Parties that the Baltic MUPPETS Coordinator and any other Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners are appointed as data processors, parties shall enter into appropriate data processing agreements as required by the GDPR.

The Beneficiary acknowledges that the Baltic MUPPETS Coordinator and any other Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners, if appointed as data processors, are not responsible for the Beneficiary's compliance with any data protection or privacy law applicable to the Beneficiary. Each of the Contracting Parties, in their respective roles as data controllers, will be responsible for their own compliance with any data protection or privacy law applicable to them as data controller.

Article 12 - Obligations imposed by the Grant Agreement to the Beneficiary

The Beneficiary receives funding from the European Commission for carrying out the sub-project [redacted] [sub-project acronym]. Under the Grant Agreement or the Consortium Agreement, some of the obligations must be imposed on the Beneficiary. Those obligations are reflected in this Agreement. The specific obligations that the Beneficiary must ensure are described in the ERDF Interregional Innovation Investments Instrument (I3) General Model Grant Agreement² in articles 12, 13, 17, 25 and 33. These articles are included in this Contract and are fully applicable to the Beneficiary.

The Beneficiary acknowledges and agrees that these obligations comprised in this Agreement and the above-mentioned obligations of the ERDF Interregional Innovation Investments Instrument (I3) General Model Grant Agreement are fully applicable to it.

Article 13 - Miscellaneous

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/i3/agr-contr/mga_i3_en.pdf

Should any provision of this Contract be or become invalid, illegal, or unenforceable, it shall not affect the validity of the remaining provisions of this Contract. In such a case, the Contracting Parties shall be entitled to request that a valid, legal, enforceable, and practicable replacement provision be negotiated which fulfils the purpose of the original provision.

The Beneficiary shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of the Coordinator or any other Baltic MUPPETS consortium partner, and nothing in this Contract shall be deemed to constitute a joint venture, agency, partnership, interest grouping or any other kind of formal business grouping or entity between the Contracting Parties or between the Beneficiary and any Baltic MUPPETS consortium partner.

No rights or obligations of the Beneficiary arising from this Contract may be assigned or transferred, in whole or in part, and no obligations of the Beneficiary may be sub-contracted, without the Coordinator's prior formal written approval; and such approval shall not exempt the Beneficiary from any of its obligations hereunder.

Although (with exception to the Coordinator and the Treasurer) the Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners and their affiliated entities are not Contracting Parties to this Contract, they are intended by the Contracting Parties to be third party beneficiaries under this Contract and accordingly shall be entitled to enforce the terms of this Contract against the Beneficiary and (without limitation) shall be entitled to the benefit of, and to enforce any exclusion of limitation of liability of the Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners contained in this Contract and any indemnity in favour of the Baltic MUPPETS consortium partners contained in this Contract.

Amendments and modifications to the text of this Agreement require a separate written agreement to be signed between all Parties. Although this Contract refers to the provisions of the CA and GA, the Beneficiary is not a party to the CA or GA but only bound towards the Coordinator by the CA and GA provisions as referred or reproduced in this Contract.

This Contract is drawn up in English language which shall govern all documents, notices, meetings, and processes relative thereto.

Article 14 - Applicable Law

This Contract shall be construed in accordance with and governed by the laws of Ireland.

Article 15 - Settlement of disputes

If the Contracting Parties are unable to resolve a dispute amicably, such dispute will be finally settled under the Rules of Arbitration of the International Chamber of Commerce by three (3) arbitrators in Dublin.

Each of the Contracting Parties to the dispute shall appoint one (1) arbitrator and the two (2) arbitrators so appointed shall elect the presiding arbitrator. Should a Party to the dispute which should appoint an arbitrator fails to do so within fourteen (14) days of the delivery of the written notice to do so from the other Party to the dispute or should the appointed arbitrators fail to reach agreement on the presiding arbitrator within fourteen (14) days after their appointment, such arbitrator shall be appointed in accordance with the Rules upon request of any of the Parties to the dispute.

The seat of arbitration shall be Dublin.

The Contracting Parties agree that the language of the arbitration, including oral hearings, written evidence, and correspondence shall be English.

APPLICANT DECLARATION OF HONOUR

Project title: _____

Project acronym: _____

On behalf of _____ [Company/ organisation name] established in _____, [Official address], VAT number¹ _____, represented for the purposes of signing and submitting the proposal and present Declaration of Honour by _____ [Name of legal representative].

By signing this document, I declare that:

1. I have the power of legally binding the above-mentioned organisation upon submitting this proposal.
2. Neither the above-mentioned company/ organisation nor any linked company/ organisation or any individual member of the proposal team has submitted any other proposal under the **Baltic MUPPETS - Innovation Call**. In case the above-mentioned company/ organisation or any individual member of the team has submitted more than one proposal to this open call, all associated proposals will be automatically excluded from the evaluation process.
3. I and the above company/ organisation that I legally represent are fully aware and duly accept all **Baltic MUPPETS - Innovation Call** rules and conditions as expressed in the respective open call documents and Annexes and will respect any evaluation decision and proposal selection.
4. The information included in the Annex X: SME Declaration document is true and legally binding.
5. All provided information in this declaration is true and legally binding.
6. I give the consent and permission to the **Baltic MUPPETS - Innovation Call** coordinator to use the attached information to contact me for any issue associated with the associated proposal.

¹ VAT is mandatory during the contract preparation. Failure to provide a valid VAT of the specific SME will result in automatic rejection of the proposal.

Company/ organisation contact information:

Title (Mr., Ms., Dr.)	
Name	
Surname	
Full address	
Country	
E-mail address	
Telephone/ Mobile phone	
Signature/ Date	

DECLARATION OF HONOUR ON EXCLUSION CRITERIA AND ABSENCE OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST

By signing this declaration of honour, I declare that all provided information below is true and legally binding both for me and for the company/ organisation that I legally represent:

1. I declare that the mentioned company/ organisation is not in one of the following situations:
 - a. Is bankrupt or being wound up, is having its affairs administered by the courts, has entered an arrangement with creditors, has suspended business activities, is the subject of proceedings concerning those matters, or is in any analogous situation arising from a similar procedure provided for in national legislation or regulations.
 - b. It or persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been convicted of an offence concerning their professional conduct by a judgment which has the force of res judicata.
 - c. Has been guilty of grave professional misconduct proven by any means which the contracting authority can justify including by decisions of the European Investment Bank and international organizations.
 - d. Is not in compliance with its obligations relating to the payment of social security contributions or the payment of taxes in accordance with the legal provisions of the country in which it is established or with those of the country of the contracting authority or those of the country where the contract is to be performed, to be proved by the deliverance of official documents issued by the local authorities, according to the local applicable rules.
 - e. It or persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been the subject of a judgment which has the force of res judicata for fraud, corruption, involvement in a criminal organization or any other illegal activity, where such illegal activity is detrimental to the Union's financial interests.
 - f. Is subject to an administrative penalty for being guilty of misrepresenting the information required by the contracting authority as a condition of participation in a grant award procedure or another procurement procedure or failing to supply this information or having been declared to be in serious breach of its obligations under contracts or grants covered by the Union's budget.
2. I declare that the natural persons with power of representation, decision-making or control over the above-mentioned company/ organisation are not in the situations referred to in (a) to (f) above.
3. I declare that:
 - a. Neither any person nor I that I know is subject to an **Baltic MUPPETS - Innovation Call** project conflict of interest.

- b. Neither any person or I that I know participates, controls, submits, or is associated in any way with more than one proposal to the **Baltic MUPPETS - Innovation Call**.
 - c. I have not made false declarations in supplying the information required by participation in the open calls of the **Baltic MUPPETS - Innovation Call** project or does not fail to supply this information.
 - d. I am not in one of the situations of exclusion, referred to in the abovementioned points (a) to (f).
 - e. I am aware and fully accept all **Baltic MUPPETS - Innovation Call** conditions and rules as expressed in the open call documents.
4. I certify that the company/ organisation that I represent:
- a. Is committed to participate in the abovementioned project.
 - b. Has stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain its activity throughout its participation in the above-mentioned project and to provide any counterpart funding necessary.
 - c. Has or will have the necessary resources as and when needed to carry out its involvement in the above-mentioned project.

Full name: <div style="background-color: yellow; width: 100%; height: 15px;"></div>	Signature and stamp (if applicable)
Done at (place) <div style="background-color: yellow; width: 100px; height: 15px;"></div> , on the <div style="background-color: yellow; width: 30px; height: 15px;"></div> (day) <div style="background-color: yellow; width: 30px; height: 15px;"></div> (month) <div style="background-color: yellow; width: 30px; height: 15px;"></div> (year)	

DECLARATION ON INFORMATION ON SME QUALIFICATION

Specific identification of the applicant enterprise:

Name or Business Name	
Address (or Registered office)	
Registration/ VAT number	
Names and titles of principal directors	

Type of enterprise (see explanatory note)

Select to indicate which case(s) applies to the applicant enterprise:

- Autonomous enterprise In this case the data filled in the box below result from the accounts of the applicant enterprise only. Fill in the declaration only, without annex.
- Partner enterprise Fill in and attach the annex (and any additional sheets), then complete the declaration by copying the results of the calculations into the box below.
- Linked enterprise

Data used to determine the category of enterprise

Calculated according to Article 6 of the Annex to the Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC on the SME definition.

Reference period (*)		
Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (**)	Balance sheet total (**)

(*) All data must be related to the last approved accounting period and calculated on an annual basis. In the case of newly established enterprises whose accounts have not yet been approved, the data to apply shall be derived from a reliable estimate made over the financial year.

(**) EUR 1 000.

Important:

Compared to the previous accounting period, there is a change regarding the data, which could result in a change of category of the applicant enterprise (micro, small, medium-sized, or big enterprise).

- No
- Yes (in this case fill in and attach a declaration regarding the previous accounting period).

Signature

Name and position of the signatory, being authorised to represent the enterprise:

I declare on my honour the accuracy of this declaration and of any annexes thereto.

Done at: (place) on (day) (month) (year)

Signature:

EXPLANATORY NOTE ON THE TYPES OF ENTERPRISES TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT FOR CALCULATING THE HEADCOUNT AND THE FINANCIAL AMOUNTS

I. TYPES OF ENTERPRISES

The definition of an SME¹ distinguishes three types of enterprise, according to their relationship with other enterprises in terms of holdings of capital or voting rights or the right to exercise a dominant influence².

Type 1: Autonomous Enterprise

This is by far the most common type of enterprise. It applies to all enterprises which are not one of the two other types of enterprise (partner or linked). An applicant enterprise is autonomous if it:

- Does not have a holding of 25%³ or more in any other enterprise,
- And is not 25%³ or more owned by any enterprise or public body or jointly by several linked enterprises or public bodies, apart from some exceptions⁴,
- And does not draw up consolidated accounts and is not included in the accounts of an enterprise which draws up consolidated accounts and is thus not a linked enterprise⁵.

Type 2: Partner Enterprise

This type represents the situation of enterprises which establish major financial partnerships with other enterprises, without the one exercising effective direct or indirect control over the other. Partners are enterprises which are not autonomous, but which are not linked to one another.

The applicant enterprise is a partner of another enterprise if:

- It has a holding or voting rights equal to or greater than 25% in the other enterprise, or the other enterprise has a holding or voting rights equal to or greater than 25% in the applicant enterprise.
- The enterprises are not linked enterprises within the meaning defined below, which means, among other things, that the voting rights of one in the other do not exceed 50%.

¹ Henceforth, the term "Definition" refers to the Annex to Commission Recommendation 2003/361/EC on the definition of SMEs.

² Definition, Article 3

³ In terms of the share of the capital or voting rights, whichever is higher is applied. To this percentage should be added the holding in that same enterprise of each enterprise that is linked to the holding company (Definition, Article 3 paragraph 2)

⁴ An enterprise may continue being considered as autonomous when this 25% threshold is reached or exceeded, if that percentage is held by the following categories of investors (provided that those are not linked with the applicant enterprise):

- a) public investment corporations, venture capital companies, individuals or groups of individuals with a regular venture capital investment activity who invest equity capital in unquoted businesses ("business angels"), provided the total investment of those business angels in the same enterprise is less than EUR 1 250 000,
- b) universities or non-profit research centres,
- c) institutional investors, including regional development funds,
- d) autonomous local authorities with an annual budget of less than EUR 10 million and less than 5000 inhabitants.

(Definition, Article 3 paragraph 2, second sub-paragraph)

⁵ - If the registered office of the enterprise is situated in a Member State which has provided for an exception to the requirement to draw up such accounts pursuant to the Seventh Council Directive 83/349/EEC of 13 June 1983, the enterprise should nevertheless check specifically whether it does not meet one or other of the conditions laid down in Article 3 paragraph 3 of the Definition.

- There are also some very rare cases in which an enterprise may be considered linked to another enterprise through a person or a group of natural persons acting jointly (Definition, Article 3 paragraph 3).

- Conversely, there are very few cases of enterprises drawing up consolidated accounts voluntarily, without being required to do so under the Seventh Directive. In that case, the enterprise is not necessarily linked and can consider itself only a partner.

To determine whether the enterprise is linked or not, in each of the three situations it should be checked whether or not the enterprise meets one or other of the conditions laid down in Article 3 paragraph 3 of the Definition, where applicable through a natural person or group of natural persons acting jointly.

- And the applicant enterprise does not draw up consolidated accounts which include the other enterprise by consolidation and is not included by consolidation in the accounts of the other enterprise or of an enterprise linked to it⁵.

Type 3: Linked Enterprise

This type corresponds to the economic situation of enterprises which form a group through the direct or indirect control of most of the voting rights (including through agreements or, in certain cases, through natural persons as shareholders), or through the ability to exercise a dominant influence on an enterprise. Such cases are thus less frequent than the two preceding types.

To avoid difficulties of interpretation for enterprises, the EC has defined this type of enterprise by taking over – wherever they are suitable for the purposes of the Definition – the conditions set out in Article 1 of Council Directive 83/349/EEC on consolidated accounts⁶, which has been applied for many years.

An enterprise thus generally knows immediately that it is linked, since it is already required under that Directive to draw up consolidated accounts or is included by consolidation in the accounts of an enterprise which is required to draw up such consolidated accounts.

The only two cases, which are however not very frequent, in which an enterprise can be considered linked although it is not already required to draw up consolidated accounts, are described in the first two indents of endnote 5 of this explanatory note. In those cases, the enterprise should check whether it meets one or other of the conditions set out in Article 3 paragraph 3 of the Definition.

II. THE HEADCOUNT AND THE ANNUAL WORK UNITS⁷

The headcount of an enterprise corresponds to the number of annual work units (AWU).

Who is included in the headcount?

- The employees of the applicant enterprise
- persons working for the enterprise being subordinate to it and considered to be employees under national law
- owner-managers
- partners engaging in a regular activity in the enterprise and benefiting from financial advantages from the enterprise.

Apprentices or students engaged in vocational training with an apprenticeship or vocational training contract are not considered in the headcount.

How is the headcount calculated?

One AWU corresponds to one person who worked full-time in the enterprise in question or on its behalf during the entire reference year. The headcount is expressed in AWUs.

The work of persons, who did not work the entire year, or who worked part-time - regardless of its duration - and seasonal work is counted as fractions of AWU.

The duration of maternity or parental leaves is not counted.

⁶ Seventh Council Directive 83/349/EEC of 13 June 1983, based on Article 54(3)(g) of the Treaty and concerning consolidated accounts (OJ L 193 of 18.7.1983, p. 1), as last amended by Directive 2001/65/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (OJ L 283 of 27.10.2001, p. 28).

⁷ Definition, Article 5.

ANNEX TO THE DECLARATION CALCULATION FOR THE PARTNER OR LINKED TYPE OF ENTREPRISE

Annexes to be enclosed if necessary

- **Annex A** if the applicant enterprise has at least one partner enterprise (and any additional sheets)
- **Annex B** if the applicant enterprise has at least one linked enterprise (and any additional sheets)

Calculation for the partner or linked type of enterprise⁸ (see explanatory note)

Reference period ⁹ :			
	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
1. Data ⁹ of the applicant enterprise or consolidated accounts (copy data from box B(1) in annex B ¹⁰)			
2. Proportionally aggregated data ⁹ of all partner enterprises (if any) (copy data from box A in annex A)			
3. Added up data ⁹ of all linked enterprises (if any) – if not included by consolidation in line 1 (copy data from box B(2) in annex B)			
Total			

(*) EUR 1 000.

NOTE: The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in the box "Data used to determine the category of enterprise" in the declaration.

⁸ Definition, Article 6 paragraphs 2 and 3

⁹ All data must be relating to the last approved accounting period and calculated on an annual basis. In the case of newly-established enterprises whose accounts have not yet been approved, the data to apply shall be derived from a reliable estimate made in the course of the financial year (Definition, Article 4).

¹⁰ The data of the enterprise, including the headcount, are determined on the basis of the accounts and other data of the enterprise or, where they exist, the consolidated accounts of the enterprise, or the consolidated accounts in which the enterprise is included through consolidation.

ANNEX A

Partner enterprises

For each enterprise for which a 'partnership sheet' has been completed (one sheet for each partner enterprise of the applicant enterprise and for any partner enterprises of any linked enterprise, of which the data is not yet included in the consolidated accounts of that linked enterprise), the data in the 'partnership box' in question should be entered in the summary table below:

BOX A

Partner enterprise (name / identification)	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
1.			
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			
7.			
Total			

(*) EUR 1 000.

(attach sheets or expand the present table, if necessary)

Reminder:

This data is the result of a proportional calculation done on the 'partnership sheet' for each direct or indirect partner enterprise.

The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in line 2 (regarding partner enterprises) of the table in the Annex to the declaration.

PARTNERSHIP SHEET

1. Specific identification of the applicant enterprise

Name or Business Name	
Address (or Registered office)	
Registration/ VAT number¹¹	
Names and titles of principal directors¹²	

2. Raw data regarding that partner enterprise

Reference period			
	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
Raw data			
(*) EUR 1 000.			

Reminder: These raw data are derived from the accounts and other data of the partner enterprise, consolidated if they exist. To those are added 100% of the data of enterprises which are linked to this partner enterprise, unless the accounts data of those linked enterprises are already included through consolidation in the accounts of the partner enterprise¹³. If necessary, add “linkage sheets” for the enterprises which are not yet included through consolidation.

3. Proportional calculation

- a) Precisely indicate the holding¹⁴ of the enterprise drawing up the declaration (or of the linked enterprise via which the relation to the partner enterprise is established) in the partner enterprise to which this sheet relates:

Also indicate the holding of the partner enterprise to which this sheet relates in the enterprise drawing up the declaration (or in the linked enterprise):

- b) The higher of these two holding percentages should be applied to the raw data entered in the previous box. The results of this proportional calculation should be given in the following table:

‘Partnership box’

Percentage:	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)

¹¹ To be determined by the Member State according to its needs

¹² Chairman (CEO), Director-General or equivalent.

¹³ Definition, Article 6 paragraph 3, first sub-paragraph

¹⁴ In terms of the share of the capital or voting rights, whichever is higher. To this holding should be added the holding of each linked enterprise in the same enterprise (Definition, Article 3 paragraph 2 first sub-paragraph).

Proportional results			
(*) EUR 1 000.			

These data should be entered in Box A in Annex A.

ANNEX B Linked enterprises

DETERMINE THE CASE APPLICABLE TO THE APPLICANT ENTERPRISE:

- Case 1:** The applicant enterprise draws up consolidated accounts or is included by consolidation in the consolidated accounts of another enterprise. (Box B(1))
- Case 2:** The applicant enterprise or one or more of the linked enterprises do not establish consolidated accounts or are not included in the consolidated accounts. (Box B(2)).

Please note: The data of the enterprises, which are linked to the applicant enterprise, are derived from their accounts and their other data, consolidated if they exist. To them are aggregated proportionally the data of any possible partner enterprise of that linked enterprise, situated immediately upstream or downstream from it, unless it has already been included through consolidation¹⁵.

CALCULATION METHODS FOR EACH CASE:

In case 1: The consolidated accounts serve as the basis for the calculation. Fill in Box B(1) below.

Box B(1)

	Headcount (*)	Annual turnover (**)	Balance sheet total (**)
Total			

(*) Where in the consolidated accounts no headcount data appears, the calculation of it is done by adding the data from the enterprises to which the enterprise in question is linked.

(**) EUR 1 000.

The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in line 1 of the table in the Annex to the declaration.

Identification of the enterprises included through consolidation

Linked enterprise (name / identification)	Address (of registered office)	Registration / VAT number (*)	Names and titles of the principal director(s) (**)
1.			
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			
7.			

¹⁵ Definition, Article 6 paragraph 3, second sub-paragraph

Identification of the enterprises included through consolidation

Linked enterprise (name / identification)	Address (of registered office)	Registration / VAT number (*)	Names and titles of the principal director(s) (**)
Total			

(*) To be determined by the Member State according to its needs

(**) Chairman (CEO), Director-General or equivalent.

Important: Partner enterprises of such a linked enterprise, which are not yet included through consolidation, are treated like direct partners of the applicant enterprise. Their data and a 'partnership sheet' should therefore be added in Annex A.

In case 2: For each linked enterprise (including links via other linked enterprises), complete a "linkage sheet" and simply add together the accounts of all the linked enterprises by filling in Box B(2) below.

Box B(2)

Enterprise No.:	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (**)	Balance sheet total (**)
1. (*)			
2. (*)			
3. (*)			
Total			

(*) attach one "linkage sheet" per enterprise

(**) EUR 1 000.

The data entered in the "Total" row of the above table should be entered in line 3 (regarding linked enterprises) of the table in the Annex to the declaration.

LINKAGE SHEET

(only for linked enterprises not included by consolidation in Box B)

1. Precise identification of the applicant enterprise

Name or Business Name	
Address (or Registered office)	
Registration/ VAT number¹⁶	
Names and titles of principal directors¹⁷	

2. Data on enterprise

Reference period			
	Headcount (AWU)	Annual turnover (*)	Balance sheet total (*)
Total			

(*) EUR 1 000.

These data should be entered in Box B(2) in Annex B.

Important: The data of the enterprises, which are linked to the applicant enterprise, are derived from their accounts and their other data, consolidated if they exist. To them are aggregated proportionally the data of any possible partner enterprise of that linked enterprise, situated immediately upstream or downstream from it, unless it has already been included through consolidation¹⁸.

Such partner enterprises are treated like direct partner enterprises of the applicant enterprise. Their data and a 'partnership sheet' have therefore to be added in Annex A.

¹⁶ To be determined by the Member State according to its needs

¹⁷ Chairman (CEO), Director-General or equivalent.

¹⁸ If the data of an enterprise are included in the consolidated accounts to a lesser proportion than the one determined under Article 6 paragraph 2, the percentage rate according to that article should be applied (Definition, Article 6 paragraph 3, second sub-paragraph).

1. ACCOUNT HOLDER INFORMATION

Account Name Holder <i>The name or title under which the account has been opened and NOT the name of the authorized agent.</i>	
Holder's Address	
Postcode	
Town/City	
Country	

Contact Person <i>Does not need to be an authorised agent.</i>	
Telephone	
Mobile phone	

2. BANK ACCOUNT INFORMATION

Bank Name	
Branch Address	
Postcode	
Town/City	
Country	
IBAN number / Account number <i>Format example: ES76 2077 0024 0031 0257 5766</i>	
SWIFT code <i>8 to 11 characters</i>	

BANK STAMP + SIGNATURE OF BANK REPRESENTATIVE	DATE + SIGNATURE OF ACCOUNT HOLDER (MANDATORY)
<p><i>The bank stamp + signature of the bank representative can be replaced with the attachment of a recent bank statement (less than 2 months).</i></p>	

